

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Dynamic lactation responses to dietary crude protein oscillation in diets adequate and deficient in metabolizable protein in Holstein cows

M. G. Erickson, G. I. Zanton, and M. A. Wattiaux

Supplementary Figure S1. Least squares means (\pm SEM) of the temporal responses to dietary treatments. Time relative to dietary change on d 25 is shown on the upper x-axis and d-within period is shown on the lower x-axis. The 2 feeding cycles are shown by shaded or unshaded backgrounds. **A.** Dry matter intake (DMI, kg/d), **B.** fat and protein corrected milk yield (FPCM; kg/12 h where $FPCM = [(1.226 \times \text{milk fat concentration}) + (0.0776 \times \text{milk true protein concentration}) + 0.2534]$), **C.** milk yield (kg/12 h), **D.** milk fat yield (kg/12 h), **E.** milk fat concentration (%), **F.** milk true protein yield (kg/12 h), **G.** milk true protein concentration (%), **H.** milk lactose yield (kg/12h), **I.** milk lactose concentration (%), **J.** milk net energy output (NE; Mcal/12 h where $NE = [(0.0929 \times \text{milk fat concentration}) + (0.0547 \times \text{milk CP concentration}) + (0.0395 \times \text{lactose concentration})]$ according to NRC 2001 equation 2-15), **K.** milk net energy concentration (Mcal/kg), **L.** milk urea-N concentration (MUN, mg/dl), and **M.** MUN yield (MUNY;g/12 h).

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Supplemental Figures (cont.)

	P-value
D	<0.001
D:F	0.002
D:F:P	0.050

	P-value
D	0.024
D:F	<0.001
D:F:P	0.322

	P-value
D	<0.001
D:F	0.056
D:F:P	0.083

	P-value
D	0.020
D:F	0.652
D:F:P	0.452

	P-value
D	0.094
D:F	<0.001
D:F:P	0.277

	P-value
D	0.048
D:F	<0.001
D:F:P	0.935

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Supplemental Figures (cont.)

	P-value
D	0.039
D:F	0.001
D:F:P	0.283

	P-value
D	0.822
D:F	0.227
D:F:P	0.623

	P-value
D	<0.001
D:F	0.002
D:F:P	0.046

	P-value
D	0.017
D:F	0.716
D:F:P	0.426

	P-value
D	<0.001
D:F	<0.001
D:F:P	0.321

	P-value
D	<0.001
D:F	<0.001
D:F:P	0.501